

TYPOGRAPHICAL, ORTHOGRAPHIC AND MORPHOLOGICAL VARIATION OF ANGLICISMS IN A CORPUS OF SPANISH NEWSPAPER TEXTS*

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ABSTRACT

It is an unarguable fact that English exerts a powerful influence over Spanish nowadays. This is revealed by the large number of Anglicisms that are found in general everyday language as well as in different specific discursive fields. Since the state of a people's language at a given moment is recorded faithfully in the press, this written mass media can be considered as an appropriate source when carrying out an analysis of the situation of the Spanish language in relation to the English loanwords that have entered it. Adopting a qualitative approach, in this piece of research I will analyse the different types of variation that characterise a series of Anglicisms found in a corpus of journalistic texts extracted from the Spanish local daily *Ideal*. By displaying these terms in context, I aim to study the way they behave when employed in Spanish surroundings. Using the findings obtained in this piece of research, I will inductively establish a classification of types of variation in Anglicisms in Present-Day Spanish.

KEYWORDS: Anglicism, press, context, variation, language in use, qualitative analysis.

RESUMEN

El inglés ejerce indiscutiblemente una notable influencia sobre el español en la actualidad. De ello dan buena cuenta los numerosos anglicismos usados en la lengua cotidiana, así como en distintos campos discursivos específicos. Dado que la prensa refleja fielmente el estado de la lengua que un pueblo posee en cada momento, podemos considerar este medio de comunicación escrito como una fuente adecuada para llevar a cabo un análisis de la situación del español en lo que a los préstamos de origen inglés se refiere. Con un enfoque cualitativo, en este trabajo analizaré los diferentes tipos de variación que caracterizan a una serie de anglicismos encontrados en un corpus de textos periodísticos del diario local español *Ideal*. Mostrando dichas palabras en contexto, me propongo estudiar la forma en la que estas se comportan cuando se emplean en textos españoles. Utilizaré los resultados obtenidos en la presente investigación para establecer, de manera inductiva, una clasificación de los tipos de variación que aparecen en los anglicismos usados en el español actual.

PALABRAS CLAVE: anglicismo, prensa, contexto, variación, lengua en uso, análisis cualitativo.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of Anglicisms in the Spanish language is a phenomenon undergoing an exponential increase. As Sánchez-Reyes Peñamaría and Durán Martínez (251) state, it is more and more frequent to find texts written in Spanish that, nonetheless, include English lexical expressions. This fact actually reflects the powerful influence that English exerts nowadays in different spheres worldwide. In Jódar Sánchez and Tuomainen's words (99), "English is undoubtedly the main linguistic influence on global communication, trade and education."

The aforementioned presence of English elements in the Spanish language can be traced by analysing the Spanish press. Indeed, this written medium is characterised by recording faithfully the state of the language a people possesses at a given moment and, at the same time, it spreads the current neologisms that have recently been coined (Medina López; Luján García; del Pino Romero; Casado Velarde). According to Esteban Asencio (8), it seems that, in Spain, the man in the street has got used to handle Anglicisms as a part of their vocabulary, obviously influenced by the mass media, mainly the press and the television.

Therefore, in this paper I will employ a corpus extracted from the Spanish contemporary press in order to carry out an analysis of the Anglicisms that its texts contain. To be precise, I will focus on the cases of variation that are reflected when these words of English origin appear in a written medium. The results obtained will allow me to establish a classification of the different kinds of variation that Anglicisms currently present.

2. REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

"In the Romance languages [...] the great majority of Anglicisms belongs to the class of nouns (80% as calculated for French) so that morphological integration regards the attribution of gender and number" (Furiassi, Pulcini and Rodríguez González, 9). This statement reveals the relevant role that the assignment of gender and the way of forming the plural number have in the process of adaptation of an Anglicism into the Spanish language.

In relation to these two issues, Diéguez Morales sheds light into some of their most important aspects. First, she remarks the fact that English gender has lost its function as a grammatical category, which only survives in the case of pronouns. Thus, since nouns, adjectives and articles do not present a specific gender in English, speakers/writers must assign them a certain gender when using them in Spanish

* I am grateful to Dr. José Luis Martínez-Dueñas Espejo, Leanne Bartley, Gülüm Tekin and my mother for their advice and support in the production of this paper.

** This piece of research has been funded by a scholarship granted by the Spanish Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports, and has been carried out at the University of Granada.

texts (in the latter language concordances are compulsory). On the grounds that her findings provide, she offers the main criteria for assigning gender to Anglicisms (126). As regards number, this same author concludes that normally the plural of Anglicisms is formed by following the English rules; however, there are also cases in which the Spanish patterns are applied —see Diéguez Morales as well—.

Pratt deals with the topic of gender and number in Anglicisms too, but from a different perspective since he carries out a series of interviews to Spanish speakers, thus focusing on the oral aspect (pronunciation), whereas Diéguez Morales tackles a corpus of written texts. This way, Pratt concentrates on issues such as the morphology of the plural in monosyllabic lexical Anglicisms that end in one or more consonants (including voiced plosives) due to the difficulty that these groups entail for those Spanish speakers who are not used to the English pronunciation.

Approaching variation in a wider perspective, there are other types of variants which characterise Anglicisms in Spanish. Some of them are motivated by diatopic reasons, as those dealt with in Rainer and Schnitzer, which can be illustrated by the case of *coste de (la) vida / costo de (la) vida* (cost-of-living —index—). Indeed, this example is geographically distributed as follows: while the first option is more frequently used in Spain, the second one commonly appears in Latin American countries. In this article the authors focus on the regional variation that exists in the Spanish terminology of economics.

Sánchez Ibáñez covers the formal variation that is observed in *on line/online/line/online*. He expounds that the presence or absence of typographical resources (such as inverted commas or italics) can be interpreted as marks of novelty or foreign character. In fact, they reveal to what extent the writer considers the word should be highlighted as foreign or not. This constitutes a relevant piece of information when tracing the evolution of an Anglicism by adopting a diachronic perspective. Considering his findings, he states that the most employed form (in the corpus he analyses, which spans from 2005 to 2012) is *on line*. Generally speaking, the use of the three options without typographical resources is higher than their marked version (although in the case of the variant *online* the tendency across the years is the opposite one), which leads the author to think that this word (in its three forms) is not perceived as a completely foreign element, thus being in a clear process of adaptation.

As far as variation in the morphology and spelling of Anglicisms is concerned, Rodríguez González carries out an analysis of different graphemic fluctuations found in Anglicisms as well as in some derivatives of Anglicisms, identifying trends and suggesting the linguistic (phonetic, morphological, stylistic) and sociolinguistic factors affecting them.

Focusing this time on Anglicisms in the area of sports, Rodríguez González covers several types of linguistic and sociolinguistic variation: (i) dialectal, (ii) lexical and morphological (iii.) stylistic and semantic, the last one including: lexical, graphematic, orthographic, phonological and morpho-phonological.

To conclude this section I will refer to Mateescu, who analyses the “group-level adaptations that Anglicisms experience” (64) in the Spanish language as they are reflected in the spelling the words show in different phases of their evolution.

3. ANALYSIS AND CLASSIFICATION PROPOSAL

This paper aims to classify the different types of variation that Anglicisms present when they are used in the Spanish contemporary press. Leaving aside socio-linguistic considerations, I will concentrate on a wide range of linguistic issues. Thus, unlike previous pieces of research that focus on one or a few types of variation (see section 2), this study covers a broad array of variation kinds. In order to do that, a sample of English words extracted from the local daily *Ideal*¹ during the period that goes from November 2010 to June 2011 will be analysed. Due to the fact that this study aims to establish a classification as wide as possible in the number of types registered rather than taking into account issues related to the frequency of use that each one presents, the data collection process has not employed any specialised software. The present piece of research constitutes a first approach to this area of study; therefore, a relatively small sample of instances representing different types of variation would be sufficient for this initial stage. Further research will be needed in order to complement the results obtained here. A manual selection of cases, based on a systematic reading of the daily, has been carried out. The instances that have been identified show fluctuations in several aspects, such as differences in the way in which the same foreign word is written, the various graphic possibilities that a term can display in its process of adaptation to the recipient language, or the rules that are adopted in the formation of its plural. These variants are easily identifiable when Anglicisms are analysed in use; thus, employing a corpus offers an interesting possibility in order to carry out this kind of study.

The following data about each word will be provided: localization (date and page), word class, the complete sentence where it is included, the original English word, a Spanish equivalent (if it exists) and some commentaries if there is something remarkable to add. In doing this, I have adapted the model provided in the project *Anglomaquia* (Martínez-Dueñas Espejo *et al.*).

By collecting the complete sentence where the word is included, it is possible to analyse how the foreign term behaves when employed in a Spanish text, e.g., the way in which its plural form is created, the gender it adopts, etc. The observation of the real linguistic contexts where the loanwords appear constitutes, therefore, a crucial factor when studying how a term from another language has been integrated into Spanish. In this piece of research, a series of examples from those found in the

¹ Out of the three editions of this newspaper (Granada, Almería and Jaén), I employ the one from Granada. Focusing on a daily published in this Spanish city when carrying out a study on Anglicisms in the press is relevant because of the specific features that characterise this place. First, the University of Granada receives a huge number of foreign students who have English as L1, L2 or FL; second, this city is a touristic destination which attracts an influx of international visitors whose mother tongue or lingua franca is English. These circumstances can influence the use of Anglicisms by the local press in the contents it devotes to leisure as well as cultural, sports or gastronomic issues. Therefore, it turns out to be reasonable to select a local newspaper from Granada in order to analyse the phenomenon of Anglicisms in the Spanish language.

press are presented. They provide the contexts of the Anglicisms, showing these loanwords in use. It allows us to observe the variation a foreign term can have; for instance, the use or absence of simple inverted commas (connected to the degree of integration the Anglicism enjoys in the recipient language), the way of writing some compounds (as two separated words, with a hyphen, or as one word), whether the term carries a Spanish graphic accent—in those cases where it would be necessary according to the target language rules—or not (the employment of this element indicates that the word is being integrated into the recipient language), or the plural form of a word. Adopting a qualitative approach, I focus on those instances of variation that are appreciable by collecting real uses of the loanwords in a corpus of texts (in this case, a corpus of journalistic texts from the daily *Ideal*). I analyse occurrences of the same word in which there is a difference between the two or among the three instances of it that I have found. Compiling real uses of Anglicisms extracted from a corpus makes it possible to recognise these cases of fluctuation clearly.

Based on the types of variation I have detected in the sample from the newspaper analysed in this study, I present here a classification proposal which will be illustrated by these real uses found in the corpus I have employed.

3.1. TYPOGRAPHICAL VARIATION

3.1.1. *Use (or absence) of simple inverted commas*

The addition of this mark indicates that the word is felt as foreign and not completely incorporated into the Spanish lexicon, so the vacillation in its employment by different (or even the same) writer(s) can be significant.

1. *frikil*/'friki', *hackerl*/'hackers', *online*/'online', *publ*/'pub', *tablet*/'tablets'
friki. 08/02/11; p. 69. Noun. "Este año no habrá ningún friki defendiendo los colores de España en el festival europeo". *Freak*. Bicho raro (*Oxford Living Dictionaries*).
'friki'. 30/06/11; p. V62.² Noun. "A diferencia de la imagen que cualquiera pueda tener de este oficio, y aunque él mismo reconoce que es un 'friki' de los videojuegos, su perfil no es el de un programador informático encerrado en su pantalla de ordenador". *Freak*. (See above, *friki*).
hacker. 24/02/11; p. V61. Noun. "Reventada por un hacker". *Hacker*. Pirata informático (*Oxford Living Dictionaries*).
'hackers'. 08/03/11; p. 36. Noun. "Y detalló que solo las informaciones «relacionadas con el G-20 interesaban a los 'hackers'»". *Hackers*. Piratas informáticos (*Oxford Living Dictionaries*). In this instance, the plural has been formed by the addition of an '-s', following therefore the English rules.

² V: '*Vivir*', a supplement which is included once a week among the pages of the newspaper *Ideal*.

online. 06/06/11; p. 49. Adjective. “Dentro de esta enorme tarea para reorganizar la defensa del copyright, la UE se ha decidido a intervenir en la lucha contra la piratería online”. Online. En línea, en Internet.

‘online’. 27/01/11; p. 69. Adjective. “Los reguladores investigan y pleitean con Google, Facebook, Microsoft y otros para defender la privacidad en tiempos de máxima transparencia y donde la reputación ‘online’ marca una vida”. Online. En línea, en Internet.

pub. 21/12/10; p. V58. Noun. “Hay tiendas y clubes sociales, pero ningún pub por orden de los primeros monarcas inquilinos, Eduardo VII y Alejandra”. Pub.

‘pub’. 09/12/10; p. 7. Noun. “«Esto significa que cuando un ‘pub’, discoteca o un bar con música, piden licencia para abrirse saben que no pueden realizar actuaciones en vivo», dice la concejala”. Pub.

tablet. 15/02/11; p. 55. Noun. “Los tablet, el 3D y los superteléfonos con sistema Android marcan tendencia”. Tablets. (Las) tabletas. *Cambridge Advanced Learner’s Dictionary*: (computer) (also tablet PC): ‘a small computer with a screen that you can write on using a special pen or that you can connect a keyboard to’ The DRAE has added this meaning as the 4th sense of the word “tableta”: ‘Dispositivo electrónico portátil con pantalla táctil y con múltiples prestaciones’.

‘tablets’. 07/01/11; p. V63. Noun. “La gran novedad tecnológica que ha traído este año son los ‘tablets’, ordenadores que se manejan a través de una pantalla táctil, sin teclado”. Tablets. (See above, tablet).

2. ‘gangster’ / gánster / gánsters:³ the form which is faithful to the original one in relation to the spelling (maintaining its foreign appearance intact) is written with inverted commas. On the contrary, the orthographically adapted ones (even with the Spanish graphic accent) do not carry this mark. Therefore, since the latter are not perceived as alien words (thanks to the mentioned adaptations), they do not need these typographical symbols. The three instances found in this study seem to point to a correlation between these two factors. However, it can only be considered as a tendency, as further research would be necessary to arrive at any satisfactory conclusions on this issue.
3. ‘vip’/‘vips’/VIP: in this case, the occurrence without inverted commas is also capitalized (although there is no direct relationship between these two features). ‘vip’. 15/02/11; back page. Noun (DRAE). “Así lo dejó patente en su desfile ante la atenta mirada del cantante Wyclef Jean, ex de The Fugees, o alguno de los concursantes del programa de televisión ‘American’s next top model’ (el hermano norteamericano de ‘Supermodelo’), presentes entre los ‘vip’ de las primeras filas”. VIP (very important person). (See below, ‘vips’). ‘vips’. 08/02/11; p. V63. Noun. “Ante los cien millones de pares de ojos —incluidos los de ‘vips’ como Hugh Jackman, John Travolta, Jennifer

³ For the data on these words, see sections 3.2.1. and 3.3.2.

Aniston, Catherine Zeta-Jones y Michael Douglas, que pagaron más de 5.000 dólares por un asiento en el palco de lujo del Cowboys Stadium de Texas—, Aguilera confundió algunas frases”. VIPs. Personalidades. DRAE: “Del ingl. *vip*, acrón. de *very important person*, persona muy importante”. VIP. 09/03/11; p. V62. Adjective. “Los multimillonarios se dedican a sacar brillo a la tarjeta de crédito VIP con más alegría que nunca”. VIP (*very important person*). (See above, ‘vip’).

3.2. ORTHOGRAPHIC VARIATION

3.2.1. *Spelling variation*⁴

1. *bikini / biquini; magazines / magacines; puzzle / puzle*: the former maintains the English form while the latter has been adapted to the Spanish orthographic rules.

bikinis. 23/12/10; p. V65. Noun. “Se las prometía felices, con la maleta a reventar de bikinis”. Bikinis. As we can read in the DRAE, this swimming costume comes from the English word “bikini,” which is named after Bikini, an atoll belonging to the Marshall Islands. This dictionary also states that there is an influence of the prefix ‘bi-’ due to the allusion to the two pieces. In relation to the gender this word adopts, although the most extended one is the masculine, the DRAE indicates that in Argentina it is employed as a feminine word. It is interesting to note that all these data appear in the entry “bikini,” while “biquini” simply refers us to the non-adapted form.

biquini. 27/01/11; p. V58. Noun. “La llegada del pequeño Bardem —o más bien Encinas, que es en realidad el apellido paterno— ensombrecería a la principal ‘exclusiva’ de la temporada pasada: las imágenes de Sara Carbonero en biquini pasando sus románticas vacaciones con Iker Casillas tras el Mundial de Sudáfrica”. Bikini. (See above, bikinis).

magacines. 18/02/11; p. 69. Noun. “Al mejor conductor de magacines optan Florentino Fernández, Pablo Motos y Ana Rosa Quintana; y ‘GH’, ‘Pekín Express’ y ‘Esta casa es una ruina’ pelean por el de mejor reality”. Magazines. Programa de entrevistas y variedades (*Oxford Living Dictionaries*). DRAE: “magacín”: “Del ingl. *magazine*, y este del fr. *magasin*”. In this dictionary, the entry “magacín” refers us to “magacín”.

magazines. 01/06/11; p. 69. Noun. “Puso en marcha los 40 principales, se atrevió con la música de vanguardia en TVE en ‘Último Grito’, dirigió programas como ‘Estudio Abierto’ o ‘Fiesta’, ha presentado magazines y publicado la friolera de cuarenta libros”. Magazines. (See above, magacines).

⁴ To know more about orthographic variation, see Diéguez Morales.

puzles. 07/02/11; p. V71. Noun. “Hoy haré huelga de ‘on-off’, vuelvo a las maquinillas desechables, a los puzles y al teléfono fijo”. Puzzles. Rompecabezas. DRAE: “puzle”: “Del ingl. *puzzle*”. See Lorenzo Criado (355).
puzzle. 24/05/11; p. 33. Noun. “Les vino a decir que se iba a tomar dos o tres días para encajar el gran puzzle de la compleja gestión municipal”. Puzzle. Rompecabezas. (See above, puzles).

2. *hippie* / *hippy*: both are employed in the donor language. In Spanish, although at present the most frequent ways of writing this word are still the original English ones (as the following two examples illustrate), when any of them is looked up in the DRAE, this dictionary refers us to the form “jipi.” According to Rodríguez González (281), when proposing variants which are not based on real use, you run the risk of not been followed and having to backtrack.

hippie. 16/02/11; p. V61. Adjective. “Pero es que la obra recrea la época hippie, con sus melenas y sus porros, que aunque no quiera alguno, existieron, y no sería bien recibido que los personajes aparecieran con cigarrillos mentolados de plástico de farmacia, o si me apuran, con parches de nicotina”. Hippie.
hippy. 09/02/11; p. V60. Adjective. “La señora iba de hippy e incluso fabricaba baratijas que luego vendía por las calles, pero a su primogénito lo matriculó en un colegio elitista de Roma, el St. George British International School”. Hippy.

3. *‘gangster’* / *gánster*: the first case remains faithful to the original spelling and is written in simple inverted commas (see below), whereas the second one has undergone a process of adaptation to the Spanish rules and appears without any mark indicating its foreign origin.

‘gangster’. 22/12/10; p. 72. Noun. “No propongo que nos matemos a tiros en carreteras poco transitadas ni que recuperemos las tradiciones ‘gangster’”. Gangster. In the DRAE we find the word “gánster,” from the English term “gangster”. See Lorenzo Criado (34, 221, 358).

gánster. 21/01/11; p. 34. Noun. “No se sabe qué le dijeron en privado, pero en las entrevistas previas Reid se refirió a él como «dictador», mientras que la congresista republicana Dana Rohrabachner le llamó «Gobierno de nazis» y «régimen de gánster que asesina a su propia gente»”. Gangster. (See above, ‘gangster’).

3.2.2. *Compounds written as two separated words, with a hyphen or as one word*

1. *online* / *online* / *on-line*: In this case, the Spanish language has adopted a variation that exists in English: the term can include a hyphen or it can appear as one word (see above, Sánchez Ibáñez).

online. 06/06/11; p. 49. Adjective. “Dentro de esta enorme tarea para reorganizar la defensa del copyright, la UE se ha decidido a intervenir en la lucha contra la piratería online”. Online. En línea, en Internet.

'online'. 27/01/11; p. 69. Adjective. "Los reguladores investigan y pleitean con Google, Facebook, Microsoft y otros para defender la privacidad en tiempos de máxima transparencia y donde la reputación 'online' marca una vida". Online. En línea, en Internet.

'on-line'. 03/02/11; p. V63. Adjective. "En España, tiendas 'on-line' de estos aparatos, como ZocoCity, aseguran que en estas Navidades «se ha disparado» su venta, aunque tampoco dan cifras". On-line. En línea, en Internet.

2. *'playoff' / 'play off'*

'playoff'. 27/06/11; p. 39. Noun. "Su manía: coger el barco antes de cada 'playoff'". Playoff. (Partido de) desempate. See Lorenzo Criado (342). *Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary*: 'an extra game in a competition played between teams or competitors who have both got the same number of points, in order to decide who wins the competition'. The DRAE does not record this Anglicism.

'play off'. 29/06/11; p. 13. Noun. "POLOS 'PLAY OFF', FUNDA NÓRDICA Y PIJAMA NIÑO de tu equipo" [capital letters in the original text]. Playoff. Eliminatoria. (See above, 'playoff').

3.2.3. *Capital letters*

'vip' / VIP: The Real Academia Española recommends the employment of small letters when writing this word: "Debe evitarse su escritura con mayúsculas, habitual en inglés por su condición original de sigla" (*Diccionario panhispánico de dudas*—hereinafter, DPD—). However, in the press this practice has not permeated completely since we find cases like the second one: VIP.

3.2.4. *Graphic accent*

1. *'gangster' / gánster, gánsters*:⁵ the form which is faithful to the original English one in relation to the spelling does not carry the graphic accent, whereas the variants that have been adapted in this respect have also adopted this Spanish element.
2. *marketing / márketing*: These two cases display an example of the adaptation of an English word to the Spanish language by means of the graphic accent. This fluctuation indicates that the word is undergoing a process of integration. Further research would be needed to establish which one is the most frequent nowadays and what the tendency showed by the evolution of their use in the last years is. The variation can be present in the recipient language for a long period of time.

⁵ For the data on these words, see sections 3.2.1. and 3.3.2.

marketing. 27/04/11; p. 58. Noun. “Carrozas y marketing para sacar lustre a la monarquía”. Marketing. Mercadotecnia. The Spanish equivalent *mercadotecnia* has not been a successful one (at least in Spain).
márketing. 16/02/11; p. V63. Noun. “Ahí radica el secreto de su éxito, aseguran los expertos en moda y en márketing”. Marketing. Mercadotecnia. (See above, marketing).

3.3. MORPHOLOGICAL VARIATION

3.3.1. Gender

1. *un fan / una fan*: there is no change in the form of the word. These entries exemplify that this Anglicism is, as the DRAE states, a “nombre masculino y femenino”.⁶
fan. 17/06/11; p. V68. Noun. “John Lennon cosechó 27.000 euros por dejar su dedicatoria en un ejemplar de su álbum ‘Double Fantasy’, 14.200 euros por una carta que escribió a mano a un fan y 12.000 por una lata de aluminio que dedicó a su hijo Julián”. Fan. Admirador, seguidor. DRAE: “Del ingl. *fan*, acort. de *fanatic*”.
fan. 14/06/11; p. V63. Noun. “Soy una gran fan suya”. Fan. Admiradora, seguidora. (See above, fan).
2. *los tablet, los ‘tablets’*: As these examples show, at the beginning of 2011 this word was considered as masculine in Spanish; however, it is employed with feminine articles nowadays, probably due to the influence of its Spanish calque’s gender (“tableta”).⁷
tablet. 15/02/11; p. 55. Noun. “Los tablet, el 3D y los superteléfonos con sistema Android marcan tendencia”. Tablets. (Las) tabletas. *Cambridge Advanced Learner’s Dictionary*: (computer) (also tablet PC): ‘a small computer with a screen that you can write on using a special pen or that you can connect a keyboard to’ The DRAE has added this meaning as the 4th sense of the word “tableta”: ‘Dispositivo electrónico portátil con pantalla táctil y con múltiples prestaciones’.
‘tablets’. 07/01/11; p. V63. Noun. “La gran novedad tecnológica que ha traído este año son los ‘tablets’, ordenadores que se manejan a través de una pantalla táctil, sin teclado”. Tablets. (See above, tablet).

⁶ Masculine and feminine noun.

⁷ As Dr. Martínez-Dueñas Espejo has accurately pointed out to me in an oral communication, the nowadays common word “Brexít”, which has been assigned the masculine article by the mass media, should actually be considered as feminine in Spanish, since “exit” corresponds to the Spanish feminine noun “salida”.

3.3.2. Plural formation

1. *fans*. 19/11/10; p. 51. Noun. “Con las fans alguna vez hemos pasado miedo; no solo por nosotros, sino por su integridad”. Fans. Admiradores/as, seguidores/as. (See above, fan). In this case, Spanish has taken the English plural form instead of forming the plural according to its own rules, i.e., adding ‘-es’ to the nouns and adjectives which end in vowel + ‘n’, e.g. *pan/panes; flan/flanes*.
2. *gánsters*. 23/12/10; p. 73. Noun. “Además, suyo es solo el piloto de la superproducción de gánsters”. Gangsters. (See above, ‘gangster’). Considering the plural form, in this case the original one has been adopted instead of following the Spanish rules. Nevertheless, although its plural has been formed according to the source language pattern, the word is not accompanied by the inverted commas (maybe because, even though it is not morphologically integrated, the use of the graphic accent as well as the simplification of the hardly pronounceable alien consonant cluster ‘-ngs-’ makes it partially—orthographically— adapted to Spanish).
3. *‘hackers’*. 08/03/11; p. 36. Noun. “Y detalló que solo las informaciones «relacionadas con el G-20 interesaban a los ‘hackers’»”. Hackers. Piratas informáticos (*Oxford Living Dictionaries*). In this instance, the plural has been formed by the addition of an ‘-s’, following therefore the English rules.
4. *pubs*. 13/12/10; p. 23. Noun. “Quien lo permite puede que en otros casos obligue a insonorizar con multas, con apercibimientos o con el cierre de locales, pubs, academias de baile...”. Pubs. It forms its plural by adding an ‘-s’ to the singular *pub*, whose final consonant (‘-b’) is not a Spanish but a foreign ending. The DPD explains that those nouns and adjectives which end in any consonant other than ‘-l’, ‘-r’, ‘-n’, ‘-d’, ‘-z’, ‘-j’, ‘-s’, ‘-x’, and ‘-ch’ should form their plural in ‘-s’ (e.g. *esnob*, pl. *esnobs*), except for a few exceptions like *club*, which admits two plural forms: *clubs* (as in the original English word) and *clubes* (which means an adaptation to the Spanish language by following its plural formation rules).
5. *radares*. 07/03/11; p. V69. Noun. “Pasen buen día y piensen que los radares solo hacen lo que les dicen, no tienen la culpa de nada”. Radars. It forms its plural following the Spanish rules. According to the DPD, those nouns and adjectives that end in a vowel + ‘r’ should add ‘-es’ to their singular form. Lorenzo Criado (183): radio detecting and ranging. American neologism.
6. *rallys*. 09/02/11; p. 70. Noun. “Albert Llovera, el piloto de rallys que quedó paraplégico tras un accidente, presentará esta noche el libro que acaba de publicar, ‘No limits’, en el que reflexiona sobre la ausencia de límites cuando se cree en uno mismo”. Rallys. See Lorenzo Criado (57, 361). DRAE: *rally*: “Voz inglesa”. In this case, neither the original English plural form has been employed nor the Spanish rule has been observed (the former would be *rallies* whereas the latter would consist of adapting the final ‘-y’ to a Spanish ending in ‘-i’ and then adding an ‘-s’). Normatively, the DPD defends an adaptation of the singular term (“rally” > “rali”) whose plural would be “ralis”.

7. *sandwiches*. 01/03/11; p. 64. Noun. “Compramos unos sandwiches y un par de refrescos”. Sandwiches. Emparedados de pan de molde. DRAE: “sándwich”: “Del ingl. *sandwich*, y este de J. Montagu, 1718-1792, cuarto conde de Sandwich, de quien se cuenta que se alimentó de esta clase de comida para no abandonar una partida de cartas”. Although in this case the word follows the Spanish rules in the formation of the plural (nouns and adjectives ending in ‘-ch’, which are all foreign terms, remain invariable or add ‘-es’ to the singular form), “sandwiches” is not a completely adapted word (it lacks the Spanish graphic accent); therefore it actually adopts the English plural form.
8. ‘*tablets*’ / *los tablets*:⁸ In these two examples we discover the variation that exists when using this word in plural: on the one hand, the original English plural form is adopted (*tablets*), whilst on the other hand, the term is employed in its singular form and is complemented by the Spanish definite plural article *los*.⁹
9. ‘*vips*’ / *los ‘vip*’: The DPD (2005) recommends the use of the form *vips*. ‘*vips*’. 08/02/11; p. V63. Noun. “Ante los cien millones de pares de ojos —incluidos los de ‘vips’ como Hugh Jackman, John Travolta, Jennifer Aniston, Catherine Zeta-Jones y Michael Douglas, que pagaron más de 5.000 dólares por un asiento en el palco de lujo del Cowboys Stadium de Texas—, Aguilera confundió algunas frases”. VIPs. Personalidades. DRAE: “Del ingl. *vip*, acrón. de *very important person*, persona muy importante”. ‘*vip*’. 15/02/11; back page. Noun (DRAE). “Así lo dejó patente en su desfile ante la atenta mirada del cantante Wyclef Jean, ex de The Fugees, o alguno de los concursantes del programa de televisión ‘American’s next top model’ (el hermano norteamericano de ‘Supermodelo’), presentes entre los ‘vip’ de las primeras filas”. VIP (very important person). (See above, ‘vips’).

3.3.3. Plural adjectives without ‘-s’/‘-es’ (as in English)

Las tradiciones ‘gangster’ (the gangster traditions): This specific case seems to be an exception, since the three results obtained by searching for “las tradiciones gangster” in Google correspond to the example found in *Ideal* (see above, section 3.2.1.). It would be interesting to look for this pattern in a wider corpus in order to find out whether it is spreading or not.

⁸ For the data on these words, see sections 3.1.1. and 3.3.1.

⁹ This pluralisation of the article while the Anglicism is kept invariable has also been recorded by Diéguez Morales.

3.3.4. *Word class*

'*vip*', '*vips*' (noun) / *VIP* (adjective)¹⁰: For the examples found in the corpus, see sections 3.2.3. and 3.3.2. The DPD provides us with the following piece of information about this Anglicism:

Voz tomada del inglés *vip* —*v*[ery] *i*[mportant] *p*[erson]—, que se usa, como sustantivo común en cuanto al género [...], con el sentido de 'persona socialmente relevante que recibe un trato especial en ciertos lugares públicos'; como adjetivo significa 'de los vips' [...]. Aunque es anglicismo admisible, se recomienda usar con preferencia, para el sustantivo, la voz española tradicional *personalidad*.

4. CONCLUSION

In this piece of research, I provide a classification of three different types of variation (which are subdivided into nine sub-kinds) that characterise Anglicisms currently employed in the Spanish language. This study brings about an in-depth treatment of the phenomenon of variation in relation to the English loanwords employed in the Spanish non-specialised press, since it covers a wide range of kinds of variation —rather than focusing only on one or a few types, as some previous pieces of research do. To be able to establish the taxonomy displayed above, I have followed an inductive method: first, I have compiled a sample of Anglicisms presenting variants, which I have extracted from a Spanish local newspaper (the daily *Ideal*), and second I have carried out an analysis of these instances, what has allowed me to identify a series of different kinds of variation that characterise Anglicisms in the recipient language at hand.

This variation that exists in several formal aspects of many borrowings can only be appreciated when we collect examples of the real use of these words and analyse them in context. As I have commented upon above, the press is a perfect source for examining features related to the writing of Anglicisms: instability in the plural forms, variation in spelling, presence or absence of simple inverted commas, etc. Thus, the instances collected illustrate that the way in which a foreign word is written in Spanish may vary, reflecting this way some deeper phenomena, such as the stage of the integration process into the recipient language at which the word currently is.

This study, therefore, aims to display an introductory view on variation in relation to the Anglicisms employed in the Spanish contemporary press. A qualitative approach has been selected, since the purpose of this piece of research is to carry out a linguistic analysis of the different kinds of typographical, orthographic and morphological variation that are found in the Anglicisms arising in Spanish

¹⁰ Sánchez Ibáñez deals with the use of the variants *online/on-line/on line* as adjectives and as adverbs.

newspapers nowadays. A quantitative approach would, otherwise, exceed the scope of the present project. Nevertheless, the latter kind of study should be implemented in more in-depth investigations on this topic in order to reach sound conclusions in terms of trying to find out patterns in the way in which the different types of variation of Anglicisms in Spanish behave. For instance, an interesting issue would be to verify whether, as time goes by, the use of simple inverted commas with a certain loanword disappears, and whether it happens with or without a period of coexistence with the non-marked form. The best tool for carrying out these larger scale analyses are the corpora of the Spanish language available online, such as those compiled by the Real Academia Española and which can be freely consulted on the website www.rae.es: CORDE, CREA and CORPES XXI. As Oncins-Martínez (217) states, “[these] electronic resources can help us track down the occurrence of foreign usages more systematically and assess the extent of their presence in Spanish more accurately.”

Reviews sent to author: 14 May 2017

Revised paper accepted for publication: 3 October 2017

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